

Author: © Andrea Puentes-Blanco (IMF-CSIC)

How to cite: Andrea Puentes-Blanco, "Henrietta Yurchenco's field recordings in Spain (1953-56): Narrating and Mapping Yurchenco's ethnomusicological research in Spain", <<https://arcg.is/1vr9PL>>.

These are the first pages of a publication in the form of a Story Map. For reading and visualizing the complete Story Map visit the following link: <https://arcg.is/1vr9PL>

The screenshot shows a digital Story Map interface. At the top left, the title "Henrietta Yurchenco's Field Recordings in Spain (1953-56)" is displayed. To the right of the title are icons for a star, a share symbol, a menu, and a user profile. Below the title is a large black and white photograph of Henrietta Yurchenco, a woman with dark hair, wearing a white top and a necklace, looking slightly to the left. To the right of the photograph, the main title "Henrietta Yurchenco's Field Recordings in Spain (1953-56)" is written in a large, dark blue serif font. Below the title, the subtitle "Narrating and Mapping Yurchenco's Ethnomusicological Research in Spain" is written in a smaller, dark blue serif font. Underneath the subtitle, it says "A story map by Andrea Puentes-Blanco (IMF-CSIC)". At the bottom of the page, there is a navigation menu with the following items: "Introduction", "Overview", "First Trip (1953)", "Second Trip (1954)", "Third Trip (1956)", "Epilogue", and "About & Credits". A small downward-pointing arrow is visible on the right side of the page.

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The screenshot shows a website with a navigation bar at the top containing the following links: [Introduction](#), [Overview](#), [First Trip \(1953\)](#), [Second Trip \(1954\)](#), [Third Trip \(1956\)](#), [Epilogue](#), and [About & Credits](#). The main content area features a large heading "Introduction" followed by three paragraphs of text. At the bottom of the page, there is a red button labeled "FMT".

[Introduction](#) [Overview](#) [First Trip \(1953\)](#) [Second Trip \(1954\)](#) [Third Trip \(1956\)](#) [Epilogue](#) [About & Credits](#)

Introduction

Between 1953 and 1956 the American ethnomusicologist [Henrietta Yurchenco](#) (1916-2007) traveled across Spain doing research and recording hundreds of traditional oral songs. This story map traces her journey through different Spanish cities and towns and relates her experiences doing fieldwork. It narrates in a simplified and schematic way her journey during her three trips to Spain between 1953 and 1956 and presents some examples of the hundreds of songs she recorded.

The sources for the story map are the original recordings in tapes that are kept at the Library of Congress (American Folklife Center), and the memoirs Yurchenco published in 2002 entitled *Around the World in 80 Years. A Musical Odyssey*, in which she shares her life and travels doing ethnomusicological research around the world.

I am in the process of indexing all of Yurchenco's recordings in Spain (1953-1956) in the open-access database [Fondo de Música Tradicional IMF-CSIC \(FMT\)](#). Very soon, and thanks to the generous assistance and help of the American Folklife Center of the Library of Congress, all the information related to Yurchenco's recordings in Spain will be indexed in the FMT.

FMT

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Introduction Overview First Trip (1953) Second Trip (1954) Third Trip (1956) Epilogue About & Credits

Overview

Henrietta Yurchenco visited Spain three times between 1953 and 1956. Explore these three trips at a glance before learning more about her journey.

First Trip (1953)

In the early summer of 1953, Henrietta Yurchenco and her five-year-old son Peter, set sail from New York to Spain. Five days later, they arrived to Lisbon, and the next day the ship finally reached its last stop, the port of La Línea de la Concepción in the province of Cádiz, right next to Gibraltar. During the summer and fall of 1953 she visited and conducted recording sessions in different locations in the provinces of Málaga and, particularly, Granada.

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